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Understanding the Constitutional impact of Panchayati Raj in Realm of Discrimination Faced by Dalit and Tribal Groups in Contemporary Times

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For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>**Ritu Kumari**Advocate
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Abstract

Gram Sabha has been constituted in every scheduled state in compliance with the Panchayati Raj Act or PESA Rules of the respective state. However, the PESA implementation guidelines have been created only in four states, namely Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Rajasthan which escapes the prominent Tribal states like Jharkhand, Telangana etc... The Gram Sabha is responsible for approving all the village developmental works, identifying beneficiaries, giving certifications of money use, and monitoring institutions and officials across all social sectors and local plans. This study aims to understand the concerns related to extension of Panchayat system to Tribal Communities and explore the reasons for failure of Panchayat regime in Scheduled areas. The secondary resource materials are used to explore and understand the dynamics. The sufferings of Dalits in the Panchayati Raj systems seem to be relieved when it comes to representation due to affirmative actions. However, when it comes their participation in the field at the grassroot level, it seems to be more problematic due to stigmatization of their status with their dignity and capabilities in the society. In order to remove such hinderances in affecting or polluting the local self-governance of India, there is a stringent need of the establishing of local and state level vigilance and monitoring institutions to specifically cater to the discriminatory concerns for the SCs and STs in the rural areas. Additionally, the struggles of women political players belonging to lower castes or tribal groups in participating in a regime full of discrimination based on patriarchy, gender as well as caste. When it comes to PESA, the moral aims have not been realised or materialised yet due to the power politics of the centre and state governments from avoiding vesting autonomy directly with the gram-Sabha. Gram-Sabha members need to be made self-aware, competent and educated to manage the administration effectively.

Keywords Human Rights, PESA, Dalits, Forest Lands, Panchayati Raj.

Introduction

The perpetual existence of the independent communities and their governance at the local level has been evident since the beginning of Ancient India passing the test of time through the Mughal as well as British rule. These communities were based on a marvellous combination of the spiritual as well as the social and the economic forces of the ancient Hindu race, and, as such, contributed more than any another cause of the preservation of the Indian people. Thus, it is that in ancient India local self-government, with all its implications, was inevitably a fundamental part of Indian Communities.

The sole evident fact that could be culled out from the history of Ancient India is that these communities at the local level were independent from the control of superior authorities when it came to governance of their intimate, social and political matters. However, this independence has been threatened by the British rule in the pre-independence era and by the Constitutional forces in the post-independence era which is evident from the fact that the Eleventh Schedule does not list 'subjects' or functions but only 'matters', and there is no mandate that the rural local bodies will perform these

functions or these would be transferred to rural local bodies or entrusted to them for implementation.

This scenario becomes more troublesome when looked from the purview of vulnerable tribal and Dalit groups located in the schedule's areas. The PESA Act of 1996 aims at establishing a nucleus of village institutions which independently allows tribals to reserve and preserve their customs and heritage and through independent governance. For tribes, the situation becomes difficult when urban population starts exploiting them, and for the Dalits caste by default since birth have played a detrimental and discriminatory factor for them. There have been many efforts by the government in the post-independence era of removing this gap between urbans and tribals, upper castes and lower castes. One of such instances was passing of 73rd Constitution amendment Act, 1992 which sought to reserve seats for the underprivileged ones in the local governing bodies so as to increase the percentage of vulnerable groups in political participation through bottoms-up approach.

However, the Panchayat systems seem to be unfavourable to the lower castes and the tribals. The rate of atrocious instances against Dalits and exploitation of vulnerable tribal groups are showing increasing trends. Dalit representatives are not provided with the respect and coordination required by the fellow mates and village members as would be required to eradicate the social evil. And the tribal population because of being innocent and naïve in their approach towards a regular life routine face several instances of human rights violation when they come in touch with the urban population and administration. This paper will examine the role of local self-governance in eradicating this discrimination amongst vulnerable groups in villages.

Objective of study

Objective 1: To understand theoretically, the issues human rights violations of Dalits in Panchayat system in the post-independence era, where discrimination based on caste is prohibited.

Objective 2: To understand the concerns related to extension of Panchayat system to Tribal Communities and explore the reasons for failure of Panchayat regime in Scheduled areas.

Objective 3: To explore the property rights concerns for the forest dwelling tribal communities, and the tussle for land acquisition.

Review of Literature

Gram Sabha has been constituted in every scheduled state in compliance with the Panchayati Raj Act or PESA Rules of the respective state. However, the PESA implementation guidelines have been created only in four states, namely Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Rajasthan which escapes the prominent Tribal states like Jharkhand, Telangana etc... The Gram Sabha is responsible for approving all the village developmental works, identifying beneficiaries, giving certifications of money use, and monitoring institutions and officials across all social sectors and local plans.[1]

The Dileep Singh Bhuria Committee report of 1995 served as the policy document based on which the 1996 PESA Act was constructed. The committee report mentioned about construction of both rural as well as urban local governance, however, the PESA Act extends the establishment of local self government only to rural areas and urban scheduled tribal areas have been kept out of the purview of the Act. It is pertinent to explore the reason for exclusion of urban tribal areas from its purview.[2]

There are many issues with the PESA Act which has failed to be successfully implemented throughout the Scheduled States in its true spirit. For example, section 4(i) of the PESA Act mentions of the word 'Consultation' before acquisition of land, however, this interpretation has been used by the government officials in an exploitative manner working against the tribals by neither acquiring tribal lands with prior informed consent, nor providing for adequate compensation and rehabilitation. Therefore, the research aims to explore the different facets of the PESA Act which tends to aggravate the issues pertaining to local self-governance, instead of mitigating them.[3]

Analysis

Panchayati Raj and Human Rights for Dalits:

Human dignity is something inherent by default and should be respected and acknowledged like that only. However, from the time of ancient India the right to live with dignity has been reserved for a few upper castes only and the caste lower in strata, were snatched away with these rights. These lower caste groups who are considered inferior humans were called as Dalits. Therefore, the caste-based stratification has led to a large number of discriminations in the society which has left its imprints on the minds of the modern population as well. Oppression of lower castes by upper castes can be exemplified by petitions in the case like that of Dalit Manav Adhikari, 2015 where the

petitioner complained of failure of the state of Rajasthan to establish vigilance and monitoring committees on state and district levels under the rules framed by the purview of section 21 SC and ST (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989. This failure of the state led to continued oppression of these lower castes, leading them to fight against for a separate independence of identity of recognition even in the post-independence era. Thereafter, in the post-independence era 73rd Constitution Amendment was brought into force in the year 1992. The amendment sought to transfer the status of Panchayati Raj from customary or conventional to legally uniform. And to reduce the degree of atrocities suffered by lower castes through representative logistics, the amendment provided of the reservation of them in the local bodies. However, the biased attitude of members of villages as well as other officers towards Dalits, and reciprocal mistrust of Dalits over the upper caste members has led this amendment and effort of the legislators futile.

The States in India is said to have a limited role in improving the stature of Dalits in the Panchayati Raj System. The trickle-down effect simply means that the development policies which if ever intended towards upper strata of the society, ignoring the lower strata, should also focus thereafter serving its purpose to the upper class, to the lower class as well. This theory suggests that the states recent development programme which were aimed at highlighting the societal issues pertaining to existence are a result of trickle-down effect which has shifted the focus from urban population to the rural and vulnerable population like that of Dalits. Before the 73rd constitutional Amendment Act the participation of the weaker sections was negligible as no seats were reserved for SCs and STs. But now this act not only reserves the seats for SCs and STs, but there is reservation even for the position of chairpersons [243D (4)]. Through these provisions, the Dalit groups have an opportunity of reorganising their status in the society. However, the barriers for participation of Dalits in the political governance regime are so deeply embedded in the society that their entrance into the decision-making regime of democracy was seen as detrimental by the Upper castes. As argued by Dubey and Singh[4], 2021 participation and representation are two separate facets of a developmental process for any vulnerable group. Representation is simply when a vulnerable groups seats are reserved in the system of governance and decision making and the struggle to get that reservation legally. Whereas, to implement that representation when a candidate from backward or vulnerable group or class, actually goes into the field and faces the challenges for respect and coordination from other oppressing class of representatives, that is know as participation. And, as per the observation of the author, participation is much more difficult than representation. The failed attempts have been made in past through writ petitions to challenge these reservations by the upper castes, who then tried to condemn the election of Dalits by means of informal or indirect discriminations or boycott campaigns which even involved violence against Dalits. Even after all these incidents if election happened, then the upper castes sought to bring a Dalit candidate to power who could succumb to their needs and demands in the political arena.

Intersectionality of Dalit Women in Panchayat:

When it came to election of Dalit women candidate to power, the situation worsened because of the intersectional discrimination being faced by them on the grounds of gender, caste as well as age long established patriarchy. This could be exemplified by the situation where the Dalit woman who was an elected representative from Tiruvallur in Tamil Nadu, wasn't allowed to host the flag on Independence Day because of her being a Dalit. Now that denial was because of being a Dalit or a woman is a separate field of intersectional research. Another incident was again in Tamil Nadu from Cuddalore district, where a woman Dalit president was allowed to sit on chair and was made to sit on ground with the Panchayat meeting.[5] There are a number of incidents to show such intersectionality of discrimination of Dalits in the political arena making the facet of participation a horrendous reality for the backward and vulnerable group ultimately discouraging them to participate in the representative capacities for welfare of the whole community. However, there are also some incidents of success of the representative efforts for the Dalits which have shown somewhat a positive trend in the states like West Bengal, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan.[6] The sole purpose for which 73rd Constitutional Amendment was made was to resolve th identity crisis for the Dalits and other backward tribes, which could be seen to be fulfilled and served by the example of string personalities like Ms. Narouti, who being a Dalit woman in a village of Rajasthan have used her representation in Panchayati Raj to not only highlight the vulnerabilities of Dalit groups, but also worked in quantum for the welfare of the whole village like no other previous leaders.

PESA and Tribal Human Rights Under Panchayati Raj:

It is pertinent to note for us of an incident related to Jharkhand where there always prevails a tussle as to how to conduct local Panchayati raj elections. The local tribal

groups like Parha Raja, Munda, etc have argued that they are stable with their stabled heads and they don't need to be a part of three tier systems and the mandates formed by Jharkhand Panchayati Raj Act, 2001 as a part of the Panchayat Establishment in Scheduled Areas Act 1996. On the other hand, other backward classes don't observe Adivasis or indigenous people a deserving bearer of reservation because of their non-progressive attitude towards Globalization, Industrialization and Modernization. This demand for de-reservation of the representation of indigenous groups in the Panchayati Raj is also based on law population of the Adivasis. However, as per reports due to failure of systematic census of Adivasis, their actual population has gone under noticed. As it is, only 2,228-gram panchayats out of 4,544-gram panchayats are reserved, and of these some 35 panchayats have recently been de-reserved.[7] The plight of Human Rights belonging to these tribal groups in the scheduled areas can be induced by the fact that they are even being a part of a systemic census of a democratic nation like India. The Adivasis don't want to trust the economic feature of flow of funds through Panchayat, and wants to sustain of direct economic gains by gram Sabha.[8] Now, it is pertinent to observe the objective behind enactment of PESA, in order to cull out the issues so deeply embedded in the society that is stopping the tribal population from even believing the welfare schemes passing from the centre.

Measuring The Success/Failure of PESA:

The entire Panchayati Raj Act of 1994 somehow failed to expand its reach up to the Scheduled areas where the tribal population's prevalence is found more. Therefore, PESA was introduced to cater to the special needs of these tribal population. Now it is a fact that Indian is home to more than 500 indigenous groups, each with its own separate culture, traditions and economic practices. Then the important question that should come to one's mind is whether one legislation like that of PESA is sufficient to cater to the special and specific needs of each of these tribes located in the scheduled areas? The answer is a positive but only theoretically yes. Section 4 of the PESA specifically empowers a state to implement adopt the institution Panchayati Raj mutatis mutandis to the specific customary needs of each state and local indigenous groups. Since ages, the Moolwasis or indigenous peoples have been exploited in many ways, and therefore, PESA was required to stop this exploitation and thereafter empower them. The PESA not only tries to establish the institutions necessary for flourishing and nurturing of tribal population, but also tries to compensate for the long-lasting injustice faced by the tribal population due to their vulnerability. This injustice is compensated by establishing exclusive control of the Panchayat areas over the natural resources and their customary practices excluding any kind of external control or pressure.[9] Now that we have understood the moral turpitude intended to be established through panchayat institutions in the scheduled areas by PESA, it is pertinent to examine the implementation regime followed for this legislation.

The implementation of PESA promises have been superficial till now. Central government although have made over the top promises to protect the interests of the tribals, however instead of vesting the rights of their interests with them, the Union along with states has vested these regulatory powers with the district authorities. The contention raised could be substantiated by the observations of Integrated Action Plan for 60 backward districts in the year 2010. This plan vested powers with the district collectorate for development of tribal areas, which followed a bottom's up approach which no where found the interest of tribals. It was almost like the government wanted to do formality of implementing the PESA Act. Tribals were being empowered without them even knowing of it, according to the whims and fancies of the government. Thereafter to support this plan, the 14th finance commission's recommended in the year 2015 that more funds should be allocated for tribal development and integration program, however as the development programs were being administered by district authorities, the autonomy for the Panchayats to use the allocated funds as per their own needs and mapping were snatched away,[10] and district authorities started regulating the implementation through district administrator's monitors, who used to indulge and interference the decision making practices of tribal panchayats and areas. However, due to absence of well trained and professional administrators in the tribal areas, it was considered appropriate to vest the powers with district collectorate, which led to bottom's up approach rather than the preferred top-down approach by the Panchayat as well as gram Sabha members.

Property Rights For The Adivasis Of India:

Another issue pertaining to tribal rights could be seen to be property rights, as acquisition by the appropriate government could be done after 'consultation' according to section 4(i) of the PESA Act without proper confirmation of the tribal population as was done in the case of Naresh Singh.[11] The arguments and ratio pertaining to the PESA and the interests of tribals residing in scheduled areas has emphasized that since the agricultural lands are the only source of income for the tribals and their customary

practices being inherently connected the forest land, its preservation, cultivation and nurturing, these lands should not be generally acquisitioned and should only be in the case of need for an important development project, with due rehabilitation and compensation in accordance with the policies of the appropriate government. The term 'consultation' also poses a problem because it provides a very minimalist liberty to the Gram Sabha to negotiate for the land acquisition by the state[12], and the term consultation does not apply for transfer of property to private individuals, therefore leaving space for the exploitation of rural and tribals by the urban population, by taking undue advantage of the vulnerable and illiteracy of the tribal groups.

It is pertinent to note the cases of transfer of land from the tribal population to non-tribals have seen a surge, which could be exemplified by the fact of Phulbani district in Orissa losing its almost 56 percent of tribal land to the non-tribals over the past three decades. The probable reason for such a surge in cases of ambiguous transfers of historically connected properties belonging to tribals is the failure of the PESA to provide for the Gram Sabha to hold the tribal lands and customary resources without any subjectivity to the recourse or actions taken by the forest officers, claiming the customary resources to be a part of reserved forests under the Forest Conservation Act of 1860. When it comes to holding the forest lands, there has always been a tussle between the forest communities and the forest police and administrative officers. The probable reason behind this tussle is that the surge in the population of the forest communities has led to the over exploitation of the forest resources, forcing the administrators to intervene and regulate the forest lands under the garb of conservation.[13] However, even after an attempt to establish its monopoly over the forest lands, the administrators were unable to protect or conserve them leading to mass depletion of forest resources in past three decades. The only way of stopping the forest officers from misusing the vulnerability of the tribal population is to educate them. However, as shown in the table 1 below, the rate of turnout seems to high amongst the tribal population. As shown in the table 1, the dropout rate of both the genders belonging to scheduled tribes are more than the other categories of students belonging to other castes cumulatively. This phenomenon might be due to availability of other economic sources and involvement in unregulated employment sectors, leading to an increase in the degree of their vulnerability.

Table 1 Dropout rates in ST and others in 2010-11

Class	Boys (%)		Girls (%)	
	ST	Other	ST	Other
I-V--	37.2	28.7	33.9	25.0
I-VIII—	54.7	40.3	55.4	41.0
I-X—	70.6	50.4	71.7	47.9

[14]

Conclusion

The sufferings of Dalits in the Panchayati Raj systems seem to be relieved when it comes to representation due to affirmative actions. However, when it comes their participation in the field at the grassroot level, it seems to be more problematic due to stigmatization of their status with their dignity and capabilities in the society. In order to remove such hinderances in affecting or polluting the local self-governance of India, there is a stringent need of the establishing of local and state level vigilance and monitoring institutions to specifically cater to the discriminatory concerns for the SCs and STs in the rural areas. The concern of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar seems to have materialized.

The policy makers also need to focus on the intersectional study on the struggles of women political players belonging to lower castes or tribal groups in participating in a regime full of discrimination based on patriarchy, gender as well as caste. When it comes to PESA, the moral aims have not been realised or materialised yet due to the power politics of the centre and state governments from avoiding vesting autonomy directly with the gram-Sabha. Gram-Sabha members need to be made self-aware, competent and educated to manage the administration effectively. Also, there is strict need for PESA to regulate private transactions related to forest, tribal or customary lands belonging to tribals when being transferred to non-tribal private players. Along with this, consultation needs to be made more stringent in the favour of tribal rights so that the injustice served to the tribal communities since ancient times can be compensated by protecting their property rights.

References

1. *Local 'Self' Government and the Constitution*, T. N. Srivastava, *Economic and Political Weekly*, Jul. 27 - Aug. 2, 2002, Vol. 37, No. 30 (Jul. 27 -Aug. 2, 2002), pp. 3190-3198
2. *Local Self Government in India*, S. N. Mallik, *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, Sep., 1929, Vo1. 145, Part 2: India (Sep., 1929), pp. 36-44
3. *PESA: The Unfinished Agenda*, KAMAL NAYAN CHOUBEY, Vol. 50, No. 8 (FEBRUARY 21, 2015), pp. 21-23 Published by: *Economic and Political Weekly*

4. Singh K. & Dubey R., *Dignity of Human Rights of Dalits through Panchayati Raj Institutions*, *Rajasthan Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 13, Oct. 2021, Chapter 3
5. Mathew G., *Panchayati Raj Institutions and Human Rights in India*, *Economic and Politically weekly*, 2003, 38(2): 155-162
6. Singh S. & Rahim C.A., *Evolving Panchayat Raj Leadership*, *Journal of Rural Development*, 1989, 8(4): 429-451
7. *Statement by Jharkhand Indigenous Peoples Forum, consisting of 48 tribal organisations, August 9, 2005*
8. Sundar N., 'Custom' and 'Democracy' in Jharkhand, *Economic and Political Weekly*, Oct. 8-14, 2005, Vol. 40, No. 41 (Oct. 8-14, 2005), pp. 4430-4434
9. *Section 4 of PESA Act, 1996*
10. *Mocking Adivasi Concerns: There is a new "plan" for the scheduled tribes, but the Adivasis themselves will have no say*, Source: *Economic and Political Weekly*, JANUARY 8-14, 2011, Vol. 46, No. 2 (JANUARY 8-14, 2011), pp. 7-8
11. *Naresh Singh & ors. v. Union of India & Ors.*, I.L.R. [2009] M.P., 730
12. De S. & Jana A.K., *DEMOCRATIC DECENTRALISATION, ALLEVIATION OF POVERTY AND ADMINISTRATION OF SCHEDULED AREAS : A FOCUS ON PESA*, *The Indian Journal of Political Science* , JAN. - MAR., 2007, Vol. 68, No. 1 (JAN. - MAR., 2007), pp. 21-40
13. *Satyajit Singh, The local in governance: Politics, Decentralization and Environment* Oxford University Press, 2016, Chapter 5, *Joint Forest Management: Decentralization, Recentralization and Devolutionary Intent*, pg.: 130-165
14. *Meena A.K., Tribal Development in India, Reality or Myth*, *Rajasthan Journal of Sociology*, Oct. 2017, Vol. 9, Chapter 3.